

Bridging the Gap: A Quantitative Study on Teacher Emotional Support and Adolescent Disruptive Behavior

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Abstract. The purpose of this study was to determine which domains of teacher-emotional support significantly influence the adolescence disruptive behavior among students. This study used the descriptive-correlational research design. The respondents of this study were 74 students from Tungkalan Elementary School, Piedad District, Davao City Division. The researcher used the Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), in the study in selecting the respondents. The gathered data were analyzed and interpreted by using the statistical tools, mean, pearson r, and Multiple linear regression. The results revealed that on the level of teacher emotional support among public school students varied across different aspects in terms of positive climate was high. In contrast, teacher sensitivity and regard for adolescent perspective was moderate. Further, on the level of adolescent disruptive behavior among public school students in terms of Aggressive school behavior and defiance was moderate. Meanwhile, Classroom defiant behavior and unimportance of school were high and was oftentimes evident. In addition, on the significant relationship between teacher emotional support and adolescent disruptive behavior, results revealed highly evident correlation between variables. Lastly, on the teacher emotional support domains significantly influence adolescent disruptive behavior. Thus, it is recommended that Teachers should strive to enhance their sense of responsiveness and sensitivity to the requirements of their students by increasing their availability and approachability. This could entail the allocation of specific periods for student consultations and the active listening of student concerns.

KEY WORDS

1. Teacher emotional support 2. adolescence disruptive behavior 3. teachers

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1. Introduction

Adolescent students devote most of their days to studying at school and face novel and complex duties, which include examinations and assessments, which vary greatly from those learned in basic education. Adolescence is a phase in which rebellion is inevitable. Disruptive teenagers often lack the ability to self-regulate their emotions and behaviors, which is a crucial social adaption skill. Consequently, adolescents are more receptive to the emotional assistance provided by elders inside the educational setting throughout this phase. The emotional connection children establish with their teacher is intimately linked to academic achievement, personal fulfillment, and their general happiness with their educational experience and

life. Students in classes with emotionally supportive teachers are believed to demonstrate enhanced academic achievement, motivation, and engagement relative to their peers.

Lobo (2023) conducted a research investigation in the Philippines examining the correlation between emotional support from teachers and students' academic involvement. The findings underscored the critical role of instructors in providing emotional support, which enhances student engagement and academic achievement. The study highlighted the significance of fostering supportive classroom interactions, especially the emotional bond between teachers and students, in improving educational performance.

Despite the expanding corpus of research on the correlation between teacher emotional support and adolescent disruptive behavior, there is a substantial gap in localized studies that specifically concentrate on Davao City. The majority of current research is mainly driven by broader, frequently Western-based contexts, which results in a lack of understanding regarding the importance of these variables in the educational environment of Davao City. Individualized interventions and support strategies that are contextually and culturally appropriate are hindered by the absence of localized data. Hence, it is imperative to address this research gap in order to develop effective, context-specific strategies that are relevant to adolescent disruptive behavior and teacher emotional support.

The study pursued answers to the ensuing objectives: a.) to determine the level of teacher emotional support among students in terms of positive climate, teacher sensitivity, and regard for adolescent perspective. b.) to determine the level of adolescent disruptive behavior students in terms of aggressive school behavior, classroom defiant behavior, unimportance of school,

and defiance to school authorities. c.) to determine if there is significant relationship between teacher emotional support and adolescent disruptive behavior among students, and d.) to determine which domains of teacher emotional support significantly influence adolescent disruptive behavior among students.

At .05 level of significance, the following hypotheses were tested: a.) There is no significant relationship between teacher emotional support and adolescent disruptive behavior among students. b.) None of the domains of teacher emotional support significantly influence adolescent disruptive behavior among students.

The study's findings highlighted the importance of teacher emotional support in reducing student misbehavior and improving engagement, benefiting multiple stakeholders. Teachers were encouraged to adopt more empathetic practices, while students experienced a more supportive learning environment. School heads could use the insights to guide professional development and resource allocation. The Department of Education gained evidence to inform policies and training programs, and future researchers were given a basis for exploring long-term impacts and developing interventions to strengthen teacher-student relationships.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—Figure 1 displayed the conceptual framework, which included the study's variables. It demonstrated that the independent variable was teacher emotional support in terms of positive climate, teacher sensitivity, and regard for adolescent perspective. The dependent variable, on the other hand, was adolescent disruptive behavior in terms of aggressive school behavior, classroom defiant behavior, unimportance of school, and defiance to school authorities.

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

2. Methodology

The following section outlines the procedures used by the researcher to perform this research study. It includes the population and sampling, instrumentation, data source, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study employed a quantitative, descriptive-correlational design to assess the relationship between teacher emotional support and adolescent disruptive behavior at Tungkalan Elementary School, Piedad District, Davao City Division. The descriptive aspect aimed to capture a detailed picture of teacher emotional support and its impact on managing student behavior, while the correlational component examined the strength and direction of the relationship between the two variables. As a non-experimental approach, it measured variables as they naturally occurred without manipulation, offering insights that could inform strategies to reduce disruptive behavior through improved emotional support from teachers.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—This study followed strict ethical standards to protect participants and ensure research integrity. It focused on the value of teacher emotional support in addressing adolescent disruptive behavior, with informed consent obtained from students and guardians. Vulnerable participants were

safeguarded through anonymity and a supportive environment, while risks were minimized using health protocols and secure data handling. The researcher, academically qualified and guided by experts, used reliable resources and maintained data confidentiality under the Data Privacy Act. There was no conflict of interest, and fairness and transparency were upheld through clear procedures, inclusion criteria, and public sharing of results.

2.3. Research Respondents—This study involved 74 Grade Four to Six students from Tungkalan Elementary School, Piedad District, Davao City Division, selected using the sample size formula by Tabachnick and Fidell (2007): $n = 50 + 8(m)$, where m represents the number of independent variables—in this case, three aspects of teacher emotional support: positive climate, teacher sensitivity, and regard for adolescent perspective. The use of universal sampling ensured that all eligible students were included, providing a comprehensive understanding of the target population. Inclusion was limited to students enrolled in the 2024–2025 school year to

ensure they had sufficient exposure to the school environment, while students below Grade Four or not enrolled at Tungkalan Elementary were excluded to maintain focus and relevance.

2.4. Research Instrument—In this study, the independent variable was teacher emotional support, measured through three dimensions: positive climate, teacher sensitivity, and regard for adolescent perspective. The dependent variable was adolescent disruptive behavior, assessed in terms of aggressive school behavior, classroom defiance, perceived unimportance of school, and defiance toward school authorities, specifically among students at Tungkalan Ele-

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—The researcher followed several key procedures for data collection. Formal permission was first obtained from the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges and the Division Superintendent, then letters were issued to school principals and class advisers. The survey instruments underwent expert content validation and pilot testing with 25 non-respondent stu-

2.6. Data Analysis—The following statistical methods were used to analyze the data: Mean was employed to assess the levels of teacher emotional support and adolescent disruptive behavior; Pearson r was used to determine the correlation between teacher emotional

mentary School, Piedad District, Davao City Division. The researcher used adapted and modified survey questionnaires: a 15-item tool from Romano et al. (2020) for teacher emotional support, and a 20-item tool from Karimy et al. (2023) for disruptive behavior, with each subscale containing five items. A panel of two education and research experts evaluated the instruments for face and content validity using Simon's (2021) rubric. Their feedback addressed clarity, alignment with the research objectives, and technical accuracy, and was incorporated into the final version to ensure the tools' validity and reliability.

dents to ensure reliability. Questionnaires were distributed face-to-face to foster rapport and allow thoughtful responses. After completion, surveys were promptly retrieved, checked for completeness, and securely stored. Data were then analyzed using statistical methods, including mean computation, Pearson correlation, and multiple regression, to examine relationships and predictive factors.

support and disruptive behavior; and Multiple Linear Regression Analysis identified which specific domain of teacher emotional support significantly influenced adolescent disruptive behavior among students at Tungkalan Elementary School, Piedad District, Davao City Division.

3. Results and Discussion

This section highlighted the results and discussion of the study. The presentation started from the descriptive analysis of teacher emotional support and adolescent disruptive behavior among public school students, followed by the discussion on the correlation between the two variables. The presentation ended with the domains of teacher emotional support significantly influences adolescent disruptive behavior among public school students.

3.1. Level of Teacher Emotional Support among Public School Students—Table 1 shows

the level of teacher emotional support among public school students which were measured

by three indicators namely: positive climate, teacher sensitivity and regard for adolescent perspective. The mean ratings of these indicators were as follows: Positive Climate (3.51) which was equivalent to high and was described as oftentimes evident. Teacher Sensitivity (3.21) which was moderate and was described as sometimes evident. Lastly, Regard for Adolescent Perspective (3.34) which was moderate and was

described as sometimes evident. The overall garnered mean was (3.35) which was described as moderate. This means that the level of teacher emotional support among public school students namely: positive climate, teacher sensitivity and regard for adolescent perspective was moderate and was sometimes observed among students of Tungkalan Elementary School, Piedad District, Davao City Division.

Table 1. Level of Teacher Emotional Support among Public School Students

No.	Item	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Positive Climate	3.51	High
2	Teacher Sensitivity	3.21	Moderate
3	Regard for Adolescent Perspective	3.34	Moderate
Overall Mean		3.31	Moderate

Legend: 1.00–1.79: Very Low, 1.80–2.59: Low, 2.60–3.39: Moderate, 3.40–4.19: High, 4.20–5.00: Very High

3.2. *Level of Adolescent Disruptive Behavior among Public School Students*—Table 2 shows the level of adolescent disruptive behavior among public school students which are measured by four indicators namely: Aggressive School Behavior, Classroom Defiant Behavior, Unimportance of School, and Defiance to School Authorities. The mean ratings of these indicators are as follows: Aggressive School Behavior (3.32) which was described as moderate and was sometimes evident. Classroom Defiant Behavior (3.61) was equivalent to high which means that it was oftentimes evident. Unimportance of School (3.51) was described

as high which means that it was oftentimes evident. And, Defiant to School Authorities (3.37) was described as moderate which means that it was sometimes evident. The four indicators/domains on the level of adolescent disruptive behavior among public school students generates an over-all mean rating of (3.45), described as oftentimes evident to the learners. This means that the level of adolescent disruptive behavior among public school students namely Aggressive School Behavior, Classroom Defiant Behavior, Unimportance of School, and Defiance to School Authorities has gained high result among learners of Tungkalan Elementary School, Piedad District, Davao City Division.

3.3. *Significant Relationship between Teacher Emotional Support and Adolescent Disruptive Behavior among Public School Students*—Table 3 displayed the data on the significant relationship between teacher emotional

support and adolescent disruptive behavior among public school students. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (Pearson r) was employed to examine the relationship between these two variables. The results revealed a

Table 2. Level of Adolescent Disruptive Behavior among Public School Students

No.	Item	Mean	Descriptive Level
1	Aggressive School Behavior	3.32	Moderate
2	Classroom Defiant Behavior	3.61	High
3	Unimportance of School	3.51	High
4	Defiant to School Authorities	3.37	Moderate
Overall Mean		3.45	High

Legend: 1.00–1.79: Very Low, 1.80–2.59: Low, 2.60–3.39: Moderate, 3.40–4.19: High, 4.20–5.00: Very High
 computed p-value of .000, which is lower than the .05 level of significance. This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating a significant relationship between teacher emotional support and the disruptive behavior of adolescents in public schools.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Teacher Emotional Support and Adolescent Disruptive Behavior of Public-School Students

Variables	r-value	Statistical Description	p-value	Decision
Teacher Emotional Support (x) Adolescent Disruptive Behavior (y)	0.86	Strong correlation	.000*	Reject Ho

[*] Significant at $p < .05$

3.4. *Domains of Teacher Emotional Support that Significantly Influence Adolescent Disruptive Behavior of Students*—Table 4 illustrated the regression analysis between various aspects of teacher emotional support—namely positive climate, teacher sensitivity, and regard for adolescents perspective—and adolescent disruptive behavior. The overall correlation yielded a computed r-value of 0.86 with a p-value of less than 0.000, indicating a strong positive correlation (Cohen et al., 2002) between these variables. This result rejects the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between teacher emotional support and adolescent disruptive behavior, demonstrating a high level of correlation as tested in the study. The findings clearly indicate a very strong significant relationship between teacher emotional support

and adolescent disruptive behavior. The analysis showed an F-value of 68.84 with a p-value of less than 0.000, demonstrating a significant model fit. Additionally, the R² value of 0.7396 suggests that 73.96 percent of the variation in adolescent disruptive behavior can be explained by the predictors, leaving the remaining percentage attributed to factors not covered by the three dimensions of teacher emotional support.

The regression coefficients reveal that all domains of teacher emotional support affect adolescent disruptive behavior. Among these domains, the positive climate, with an unstandardized coefficient of =0.378, exhibited the most significant influence on adolescent disruptive behavior, as evidenced by p-values below 0.05. Consequently, this result leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. These findings

highlight the critical role that teacher-student relationships, particularly a positive classroom environment, play in mitigating disruptive behavior.

Table 4.Domains of Teacher Emotional Support that Significantly Influence Adolescent Disruptive Behavior of Students

Teacher Emotional Support	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-value	p-value	Decision @ = 0.05
Constant	1.908	0.209	–	4.668	.000*	–
Positive Climate	0.378	0.085	0.102	1.086	.001*	Reject Ho
Teacher Sensitivity	0.297	0.079	0.601	6.432	.000*	Reject Ho
Regard for Adolescent Perspective	0.324	0.074	0.605	6.234	.000*	Reject Ho

[*] Significant at p <.05

Dependent Variable: Adolescent Disruptive Behavior of Students

Regression Statistics: R = 0.86, R² = 0.7396, F-ratio = 68.844, p-value = .000

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study aimed to determine the level of the teacher emotional support and adolescent disruptive behavior among public school students. In addition, it also seeks to have empirical evidence on the perceived relationship of teacher emotional support and adolescent disruptive behavior. Further, data were gone through scientific analysis to pin out which domains of teacher emotional support could significantly influence the adolescent disruptive behavior. The following are the significant findings:

4.1. Findings—Based on the above result, the teacher emotional support—namely positive climate, teacher sensitivity, and regard for adolescent perspective significantly influences adolescent disruptive behavior by registering a p-value of .000 which is less than .05 in the level of significance. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Further, the result indicates that for every unit increase in the three domains of teacher emotional support predictors, the adolescent disruptive behavior will increase by 1.908 holding other factors constant.

4.2. Conclusions—The findings reveal that teacher emotional support in public schools is effective in fostering a positive classroom climate, with teachers promoting respect, fairness, and collaboration. However, while teacher sensitivity is moderate, it lacks consistency, and

support for student perspectives is also inconsistent. This aligns with Bowlby’s Attachment Theory (1978), which suggests that consistent emotional support from teachers is key to forming secure attachments that promote emotional stability and adaptive behavior. The inconsistency in teacher responsiveness may hinder the development of secure emotional bonds, limiting the positive impact on students’ behavior and learning. Improving this consistency could enhance teacher-student attachment and, in turn, reduce disruptive behaviors.

Adolescent disruptive behavior in public schools varies, with more common issues like texting and classroom defiance than severe actions like vandalism. Other behaviors, such as lateness and disengagement, highlight the need for better student engagement strategies. These

findings align with Doyle's (2006) Ecological Approach, which emphasizes the interaction between individual, classroom, and school factors. Disruptions may arise not only from individual traits but also from the broader classroom environment. Strengthening teacher emotional support in this context can reduce disruptions by improving both student engagement and classroom dynamics.

The findings show a significant relationship between teacher emotional support and reduced adolescent disruptive behavior. Positive emotional support, including fostering a positive classroom climate and considering student perspectives, leads to a more conducive learning environment. This supports Erikson's (1980) Psychosocial Theory, suggesting that consistent teacher support helps students navigate key developmental tasks like identity formation and autonomy. By promoting trust and competence, teachers can reduce feelings of insecurity that contribute to disruptive behavior, ultimately improving both classroom behavior and psychosocial development.

The analysis reveals a strong correlation between teacher emotional support and reduced disruptive behavior. The positive classroom climate is the most influential aspect of this support. These results underscore the importance of Bowlby's Attachment Theory and Erikson's Psychosocial Theory, highlighting the role of teacher-student relationships in shaping student behavior. Furthermore, Doyle's Ecological Ap-

proach emphasizes that the school environment, influenced by teacher support, plays a crucial role in student engagement and success. The findings suggest that enhancing teacher emotional support can effectively reduce disruptive behaviors by fostering both secure emotional attachments and a positive classroom environment.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings, the following recommendations are offered: Teachers should enhance their responsiveness and sensitivity by being more available to students and actively listening to their concerns, while also integrating student feedback into their teaching. Students should take an active role in fostering a positive classroom environment by participating in activities, respecting peers and teachers, and taking responsibility for their behavior. School heads are encouraged to implement professional development programs focused on strengthening teacher emotional support, especially in understanding and addressing student needs. The Department of Education should promote policies that prioritize teacher emotional support by offering training resources, evaluating classroom emotional climates, and sharing best practices in student behavior management. Future researchers should explore the long-term impact of improved teacher emotional support on student behavior and assess the effectiveness of targeted interventions over time.

5. References

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